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Ivana V. Bajšanski, Dragan D. Milošević, Stevan M. Savić

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Abstract: The objective of this paper is to present and apply automatic algorithms to evaluate and improve non-stationary outdoor thermal comfort in urban areas. The effects of urban planning on thermal sensations are analyzed in three linear urban street designs and in non-linear arrangement of the streets with no vegetation in Novi Sad, Serbia. A temporal analysis is performed for extreme hot and cold days using universal thermal climate index (UTCI) simulations in the Grasshopper program. In future linear street design, the frequencies of the greatest thermal stress situations substantially decrease on hot summer days and slightly increase on cold winter days. Past, present, and future urban designs of linear street are compared, and the largest UTCI decreases are noted at 10, 17 and 18 UTC on hot summer days at 11 UTC on cold winter days. Future planned and proposed urban design of linear and non-linear streets is compared and the largest UTCI decreases are noted at 10 UTC on summer day and increases at 11 UTC in winter day. The building height and density increases in the future street design will modify the thermal environment. The proposed automatic algorithms are applicable for the analysis of human thermal comfort in various urban designs and climates.

Evaluation and improvement of outdoor thermal comfort in urban areas on extreme temperature days: applications of automatic algorithms

Ivana V. Bajšanski^a, Dragan D. Milošević^{b*}, Stevan M. Savić^b

^a*Department of Architecture and Urban Planning, Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 6, 21000 Novi Sad*

^b*Climatology and Hydrology Research Centre, Faculty of Science, University of Novi Sad, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia*

* *Corresponding author, Tel.: +381640343927, Fax: 021459696. E-mail address: dragan.milosevic@dgt.uns.ac.rs (D. D. Milošević)*

1. Introduction

Urban landscape creates a climate that influences human comfort conditions and this is a well-established fact. Nevertheless, climate information often has low impact on the urban planning process in practice. One of the main reasons for this is the lack of easily accessible climate information and tools for urban planners [1]. This could be solved through good communication and cooperation between urban climatologists and planners and with the development of user-friendly tools [1, 2].

Models such as ENVI-met [3] and RayMan [4] are usually used by urban climatologists and meteorologists in their analysis of outdoor thermal comfort in urban areas [4-7]. There is a strong need for the development of user-friendly tools suitable for urban planners in order to achieve higher impact of climate information on planning process [1].

From recently, human thermal comfort conditions can be assessed via UTCI calculations using Ladybug software for environmental analysis. This software is familiar and user-friendly for urban planners and architects and supports the decision-making process during the initial stage of design [8]. Integrating the UTCI calculation into Ladybug enables cooperation among architects, urban planners, urban bio-meteorologists and climatologists on thermal comfort issues in urban planning.

UTCI was developed mostly from European data [9], but it also performed well in the analysis of urban outdoor thermal environments in Canada and Korea [10] and in the sub-tropical climate of southern Brasil [9]. For the moderate climate of Freiburg (Southwest Germany) UTCI and other indices are found to be well correlated [11]. In contrast, the index showed limitations in hot climates (Doha, Qatar) when compared to other indices, such as PET. This is a consequence of a very narrow range for the input parameters UTCI accepts and due to this it is limited to moderate meteorological conditions [12].

The aims of this paper are to introduce new possibilities (software packages) for the

evaluation and improvement of outdoor human thermal comfort in built urban environments. We developed and applied an algorithm for the evaluation of non-stationary outdoor thermal comfort conditions. Furthermore, we developed and applied algorithm for automatically changing buildings heights in order to improve outdoor thermal comfort using the algorithm for automatically changing body locations. The potential of the algorithms to solve a range of urban scenarios is illustrated through the analysis of outdoor thermal comfort for linear and non-linear streets arrangement without vegetation. To evaluate the benefits of these algorithms we performed temporal analyses for extreme temperature days.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area and investigated locations in city

Novi Sad is located in the northern part of the Republic of Serbia ($45^{\circ}15' N$ and $19^{\circ}50' E$) (Fig. 1) on a gentle relief between 80 and 86 m a.s.l. Hence, the climate is generally free of orographic effects. Based on a population of 340 000, Novi Sad is the second largest metropolitan region in Serbia. The Danube River passes through the southern and eastern edges of the urban area; its width varies from 260 to 680 metres. The relatively narrow Danube-Tisza-Danube Canal passes through the northern part of the city. The northern slopes of the Fruška Gora Mountains (which have a maximum peak of 538 m a.s.l.) are located south of the Novi Sad urban area [13].

Fig. 1. Built-up area of Novi Sad, its location in Europe and in the Republic of Serbia.

Evaluation of outdoor thermal comfort in three urban designs of Đorđe Rajković Street, which is located in the old city district of Podbara near Novi Sad downtown, was investigated. The street is linear, 91 m long and has an E-W orientation in all three urban designs and pedestrians and

vehicles use it.

The past urban design from 2001 was characterized by 100% single-family housing with 5 m tall detached and attached houses. The present (2014) urban design is a combination of single (attached houses) and multi-family housing (attached buildings), in which the heights of houses are 5 m and the heights of buildings are 12 m (3 stories) or 15 m (4 stories). The investigated street is part of the Local climate zone (LCZ) 2 area, a compact midrise class [14] characterized by dense mix of midrise buildings (3-4 stories) with no trees. Land cover is mostly paved and brick, tile, and concrete are used as construction materials. According to the General Urban Plan of the City of Novi Sad for the year 2021 [15], the remaining houses will be torn down and replaced with 3- or 4-story buildings. Consequently, future urban designs will be 100% multi-family housing in 12-m and 15-m attached buildings.

Furthermore, improvements of outdoor thermal comfort conditions were tested in linear Đorđe Rajković Street and in urban fabric with non-linear streets (473 m length). Urban design of non-linear streets is appropriate representation of Podbara city district and represents a combination of attached and detached multi-family housing with buildings heights of 9 m (2 stories), 12 m (3 stories) and 18 m (5 stories).

2.2. Climate and weather database

Novi Sad has a Cfb climate (temperate climate, fully humid, and warm summers, with at least four $T_{\text{mon}} \geq +10 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) according to the Köppen-Geiger climate classification [16]. The mean annual air temperature in Novi Sad is 11.2 °C, with an annual range of 22.1 °C. The coldest month is January (-0.4 °C), and the warmest month is July (21.7 °C). During the last decades in Novi Sad periods with strong heat stress (for the summer season) and extreme cold stress (for winter) have increased and decreased, respectively [17]. The mean annual precipitation is 598 mm, with the lowest values in February (32 mm) and the highest values in June (73 mm) (based on data from

1949 to 2013).

An urban climate monitoring network system in Novi Sad was developed under the URBAN-PATH project [18] in 2013 and 2014. The network consists of 27 measurement stations located in nine LCZs of the city [19]. The measurement stations are equipped with ChipCap 2 sensors in a radiation protection shield (nine radiation plates) with dimensions of 200x240 mm. Fully calibrated humidity and temperature sensors are developed by the General Electric Measurement & Control Company. The accuracy of the air temperature (relative humidity) sensor is ± 0.3 °C ($\pm 2\%$). The sensors and all equipment were installed at 4 m above the ground on arms (50 cm long) fixed to selected lampposts (Fig. 2a). Central processor, EPROM chip as data storage, GPRS/EDGE/3G modem, battery and charger are settled in the station console. Stations measure the values every minute and every 10 minutes send the readings related to air temperature, relative humidity, battery voltage, status value and other technical information to the main server. The stations times are in Universal Time Coordinated (UTC) and are regularly synchronized by the main server (located at the University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Science - UNSPMF).

The UTCI is calculated to assess outdoor thermal conditions (Table 1) in terms of a one-dimensional quantity summarizing the interaction of the environmental temperature (T), wind speed (v), relative humidity (RH) and longwave and shortwave radiant heat fluxes (g) [9].

Table 1. UTCI assessment scale [20].

T and RH data from urban climate monitoring network station 2-3 (the first number is the LCZ class, and the second number is the station number in the LCZ class) were selected for the assessment of outdoor thermal comfort in the investigated streets. The measurement site is located on a street with E-W orientation, 400 m to the south of Đorđe Rajković Street (Fig. 2b). Surface properties of the environment around measurement station (Table 2) and the research streets are similar.

Fig. 2. Location of station 2-3: a) station mounted on a lamppost, b) distance of the station from the investigated Đorđe Rajković Street. NOTE: The last aerial photograph of the Novi Sad urban area is from 2009.

Table 2. Surface properties of the 250 m radius environment around measurement station 2-3. The abbreviations refer to surface properties: HRE – height of roughness elements, SVF – sky view factor, BSF – building surface factor, ISF – impervious surface factor, PSF – pervious surface factor, and ALB – albedo

The hourly v for Novi Sad was collected from daily WRF model [22] predictions initiated at 0 UTC for the Pannonian Basin using National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration/National Centers for Environmental Prediction Global Forecast (NOAA/NCEP GFS) [23]. Wind speed data was transferred to the microenvironment using Roughness Mapping Tool [24] in order to calculate wind correction factor. Furthermore, UTCI wind speed data were converted to 10 m height using UTCI's wind speed converting formula [9].

The hourly g data for the analysis were used from the dataset for the city of Belgrade (< 100 km to the south of Novi Sad), which is available from Energy Plus weather data [25]. Because of the small differences in the geographical latitudes, the distance between the two cities, and their locations in plains, it was assumed that global solar radiation data for Belgrade could be used for Novi Sad on the cloudless days selected for this study. The influence of the urban geometry on g was taken into account by using Ladybug for the UTCI calculation in the investigated streets (for more details, see section 2.3.1.).

Days from extreme hot and cold periods during 2014 were selected for the assessment of the UTCI changes in three urban designs of the investigated streets. According to the Republic Hydrometeorological Service Bulletin [26], the most intensive heat wave occurred from the 5th to 10th of July, and the warmest day during this 6-day period was July 7th (a hot and calm summer day). A very strong cold spell period occurred from the 27th to 31st of December [27], in which the coldest day was December 31st (cold and clear sky winter day). According to the station 2-3 measurements, the maximum air temperature on July 7th reached 35.1 °C, while the minimum on

2.3. Methodology

2.3.1. Methodology for the UTCI calculation in Ladybug

The workflow for UTCI calculation in Ladybug consists of several phases. Necessary phases are shown as follows (Table 3):

1. In the first phase, 3D model can be generated into Rhinoceros (CAD software) that provide digital environment for the parametric study. The generated 3D models of the analysed streets include surrounding buildings, houses and footways. Afterwards, geometric referencing of 3D models was performed on the algorithm in a graphical algorithm editor Grasshopper (plug-in Rhinoceros) to allow for parameterization of elements of the 3D model.

2. The second phase refers to the Solar Adjusted Mean Radiant Temperature (SAMRT) calculation using the Outdoor Solar Temperature Adjustor component in Ladybug (plug-in Grasshopper). The hourly SAMRT value can be calculated by considering data imported into the algorithm as an .epw (Energy Plus Weather) file consisting of: location (latitude, longitude and altitude) and hourly values of T , RH , v and g .

The calculation also includes:

- Body posture (standing or sitting; here, the manikin (180 cm tall) is standing)
- Rotation angle of the body (0 to 360°). The front of the body has to be perpendicular to the footway line (straight or curved), i.e. perpendicular to the tangent line of point that represents body location.
- Ground reflectivity (between 0 and 1; here, the ground reflectivity of the concrete was 0.23 [28])
- Clothing absorptivity (between 0 and 0.99; here, the manikin has clothing absorptivity of 0.46 for a summer day and 0.99 for a winter day, as defined by the clothing function of

Ladybug)

- Analysis period of the year, month, day and hour (July 7th (00-24h) and December 31st (00-24h))
- Context shading (3D model of surrounding buildings and houses)
- Body location

3. The third phase refers to the UTCI calculation at each body location predetermined by algorithm (more details in Section 2.3.2.). UTCI calculations are based on T , RH and v imported from an .epw file, and calculated SAMRT.

4. The fourth phase includes exporting all numerical results of UTCI values (expressed in °C) from Grasshopper to Microsoft Office Excel. The results are exported to sort the results in columns and detect all hourly values for a certain analysis period and weather data.

Table 3. Methodology for the UTCI calculation in Ladybug.

The UTCI values calculated by the algorithm were compared with the calculated UTCI values at the official website (available as software at: <http://www.utci.org/utcineu/utcineu.php>) to verify the accuracy of the results obtained with the algorithm. After inputting the necessary data on the official website, the UTCI results had the same values as the algorithm calculations.

2.3.2. *Developed algorithm for automatically changing body location in built urban environments*

The algorithm created in this paper allows to automatically changing body location in built urban environment in order to calculate UTCI values. The main geometric parameter is one-dimensional linear or non-linear line that represents footway with certain length (l). Footway can be divided into same segments length (s). Start and end points of the segments represent a group of points (n), marked with number from 0 to $n - 1$. Each point represents a potential body location. To provide minimal two locations, segment length must be lesser or equal to length of footway, $s \leq l$

(Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Flowchart of algorithm for automatically changing body location.

By referencing 3D model of urban environment from Rhinoceros into Grasshopper, the geometry of the buildings, houses and footways are fixed on site, whereas body location on the footway is automatically changed by the algorithm and UTCI calculations are performed. After calculating the UTCI value at one position, the position of the body changes, and a calculation of the UTCI value at a new position is performed. The algorithm calculates the UTCI values until all predetermined body locations are examined. The number of UTCI simulation results is equal to the number of body locations on the footway. Calculations were performed at one footway at a time (Fig. 4). The process of calculating UTCI values at 19 positions on each of three footways for each hour during a 24-h period (1368 UTCI values) lasts < 10 min. When the street is linear, the UTCI calculation can be performed at one footway or at all footways at the same time. When the streets are non-linear, footways have to be connected into one group of straight and curved lines and UTCI will be calculated.

2.3.3. Developed algorithm for automatically changing buildings heights

The algorithm for automatically changing buildings heights in order to improve outdoor thermal comfort was created. Models of streets containing closed poly lines representing the buildings bases and straight and/or curved lines representing the footway(s) were created in Rhinoceros. Afterwards, a list of numerical values equal to the number of buildings bases and the code that generates the final list of all possible permutations with repetition of the numerical values was created in Grasshopper. One numerical value from the list is appropriate to height of one building in Grasshopper. The geometry from Rhinoceros is referenced in Grasshopper and possible buildings heights arrangement, based on list of permutations, was generated. Footway(s) and possible buildings heights arrangement are fixed on site, whereas the body location on the

footway(s) is automatically changed and UTCI calculations are performed. When the UTCI calculation is finished in one possible buildings heights arrangement, the algorithm repeats UTCI calculation in a new buildings heights arrangement until the list of all permutations is finished. The final (proposed) urban design of the street is chosen based on minimum (summer day) or maximum (winter day) UTCI value. The flow of data between the different software is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. The flow of data between the different software.

2.3.4. Shadow simulations

In order to explain the maximum UTCI differences between urban designs, shadows of urban geometry were created in Ecotect software for solar analysis. Following input data were defined in order to determine appropriate daily sun path and shadows:

- Location data of the analyzed street (latitude, longitude and altitude)
- Analyzed days and hours (July 7th and December 31st)
- Geometry input (3D model of investigated street)

3. Results

The algorithms were applied in two types of urban designs. Firstly, algorithm was applied for automatically changing body location in order to evaluate outdoor thermal comfort in linear street in three urban designs (Fig. 5a-c).

Fig. 5. The geometry of the street with determined body locations on the footways: a) previous urban design, b) present urban design and c) future urban design.

Secondly, another algorithm for automatically changing current buildings heights in order to improve outdoor thermal comfort was applied. Calculations were performed in linear street and in urban fabric with non-linear arrangement of the streets.

3.1. Evaluation of thermal comfort during hot summer day in various urban designs

A hot summer day in three urban designs of the street is characterized as having no thermal stress after midnight, while the early morning and late evening hours are characterized by moderate heat stress. The rest of the day is characterized by strong and very strong heat stress (Fig. 6a-c).

Fig. 6. The average UTCI values for 7th July 2014 at all predetermined body locations at: a) the northern footway, b) the middle of the street, and c) the southern footway.

When comparing past, present and future urban design, very strong heat stress category showed the most substantial change. Very strong heat stress decreased in the future by 3.8 % in the middle of the street, 6.6 % at northern footway and 9.8 % at southern footway. Contrary to this, the frequency of no thermal stress situations did not change substantially (Table 4).

Table 4. UTCI stress categories [%] for the three urban street designs during a hot summer day (July 7th 2014).

The maximum UTCI differences between past, present and future urban designs were noted at shadowed body locations (Fig. 7a-c). Calculated UTCI decrease in the future is from 2.0 °C to 2.4 °C in the middle of the street (18 UTC), from 3.0 °C to 4.5 °C at northern footway (17 UTC) and from 4.5 °C to 6.1 °C on southern footway (10 UTC).

Fig. 7. Sun's path and shadows of the urban geometry on 7th July 2014 in: a) past urban design, b) present urban design, and c) future urban design.

3.2. Evaluation of thermal comfort during cold winter day in various urban designs

A cold winter day in three urban designs is characterized by strong cold stress on all footways from 3 to 9 UTC and at 14 UTC (due to the wind speed increase). The rest of the day is characterized by moderate cold stress on all footways (Fig. 8a-c).

Fig. 8. The average UTCI values for 31st December 2014 at all predetermined body locations at: a) the northern footway, b) the middle of the street, and c) the southern footway.

When comparing past, present and future urban design, strong cold stress category increased and moderate cold stress decreased. Increase of strong cold stress in the future is from 0.9 % in the middle of the street to 1.7 % at northern footway and 3.5 % at southern footway (Table 5).

Table 5. UTCI stress categories [%] in the three urban street designs on a cold winter day (31st December 2014).

The maximum UTCI differences between past, present and future urban designs were noted at shadowed body locations at 11 UTC (Fig. 9a-c). Calculated UTCI decrease in the future is from 0.2 °C to 3.1 °C on southern footway, from 1.5 °C to 3.2 °C on northern footway and from 1.9 °C to 3.2 °C in the middle of the street.

Fig. 9. Sun's path and shadows of the urban geometry on 31st December 2014 in: a) past urban design, b) present urban design, and c) future urban design.

3.3. Improvement of thermal comfort during extreme temperature days in linear and non-linear streets

The UTCI decrease in linear street between future planned and proposed urban design was up to 2.9 °C at 10 UTC on summer day, while during the winter day the UTCI increase was up to 1.7 °C at 11 UTC. The differences between future planned and proposed buildings heights arrangement are shown at Figure 10a-c.

Fig. 10. The buildings heights arrangement of the linear street: a) future planned urban design, b) proposed urban design in summer and c) proposed urban design in winter.

The UTCI decrease in non-linear streets between future planned and proposed urban designs (Fig. 11a-c) was up to 3.9 °C at 10 UTC on summer day, while during the winter day the UTCI increase was up to 1.1 °C at 11 UTC.

Fig. 11. The buildings heights arrangement of the non-linear streets: a) future planned urban design, b) proposed urban design in summer and c) proposed urban design in winter.

4. Discussion

Urban geometry strongly influences the thermal comfort at street level and has implications for urban planning and design [29]. There is a strong need for human/bio-meteorological and urban climate models in researching thermal comfort to aid urban planners and architects [2]. Ladybug benefits allow the user to explore the direct relationship between environmental data and the generation of the design through numerical and graphical data outputs that are highly integrated with the building geometry [8].

Grasshopper software and its existing plug-ins enable the calculation of UTCI value at n number of body locations at the same time. This is appropriate solution for small urban environment with few body locations. In case of investigating thermal comfort in large urban areas (e.g.

boulevards, squares, industrial areas, large parking lots, etc.) it is difficult for the computer (e.g. computer stops working or turns off) to calculate UTCI values at large number of body locations. In order to solve this problem, authors developed automatic algorithm procedure that enables the calculation of UTCI value at one body location at a time on user-defined number of positions.

The algorithm procedure for automatically changing body locations in order to calculate UTCI at each predetermined position was developed and applied. This is an advantage compared to the stationary small-scale model RayMan that cannot be applied to assess non-stationary thermal conditions of single persons (e.g. if they move from the sunny to the shaded sidewalk within a street canyon) [4]. Ease of 3D modeling (e.g. building geometry such as curved shapes, sloped elevations and shading devices) and higher resolution of visual representations of the built environment are advantages when compared to RayMan and ENVI-met. Higher spatial resolution (e.g. set-up of body location at every cm if preferred) of the UTCI results is advantage when compared to the ENVI-met model. Furthermore, it is possible to assign different values of manikin characteristics (rotation angle of the body, body posture and clothing absorptivity) for each body location. When the body location is automatically changed, algorithm uses the assigned manikin characteristics values at each body location for UTCI calculation. Hence, the thermal comfort of investigated urban environments can be assessed in a sophisticated manner.

The rotation angle of the body in relation to the Sun can have a large effect on the amount of radiation that falls on it. If the rotation angle of the body is changed (e.g. 5° , 95° , 185° and 275°), the UTCI differences are from 0.2°C to 0.9°C . Therefore, it is very important that the front of the body of the pedestrian is perpendicular to the footway line. If the body posture is changed (e.g. standing, sitting or lying down) it affects the final UTCI result. As an example, calculated UTCI differences between standing and sitting manikin at one body location is 0.2°C and between standing and lying down is 1.2°C . Changes in clothing absorptivity values also affect outdoor thermal comfort. For summer day the value of clothing absorptivity is set to 0.46 in order to correspond to a manikin dressed in shorts and T-shirts. When the clothing absorptivity is changed

from 0.46 to 0.4 (0.5) the differences in UTCI values are 0.5 °C (0.3 °C). For winter day the clothing absorptivity is 0.99 and corresponds to a manikin dressed in a 3-piece suit. When the clothing absorptivity is changed from 0.99 to 0.8 (0.9) the differences in UTCI values are 0.2 °C (0.1 °C).

Different lengths and geometry of non-linear streets and footways are noticed when compared to linear arrangement of the street. If the UTCI calculations were performed in the same manner for non-linear streets as for the linear streets, problems would arise with the rotation angle of the body and different numbers of body locations at footways. When algorithm automatically changes body location on linear footway, the rotation angle of the body is not changed, while on non-linear footways it has to be changed considering direction of tangent line in each point representing body location. Furthermore, it is necessary to connect all footways in non-linear arrangement of streets into one line and calculate UTCI value at one by one location.

Benefit of the Grasshopper is that it allows for the urban design optimization by creation and application of algorithms [30, 31]. The algorithm for automatically changing building heights in order to achieve improved outdoor thermal comfort was created and applied in urban environments with linear and non-linear arrangement of the streets. Results showed that different buildings heights arrangements were obtained for summer and winter day. Due to this, it is a complicated task facing architects and urban planners to choose urban design ensuring improved thermal comfort during extreme temperature situations in urban areas. Similar results were obtained in previous studies that examined the effects of shading on outdoor thermal environments [6, 29, 32-34].

A disadvantage of the applied software is that it takes into account the influence of vegetation as any solid form that casts a full shadow. Due to this, for the urban environments with vegetation it is better to use models RayMan and ENVI-met for the research of outdoor thermal comfort. Furthermore, similar to RayMan model it is not possible to consider building materiality in Ladybug.

5. Conclusion

In this paper are introduced new possibilities for the evaluation and improvement of thermal comfort in built urban environments. A new approach presents the combination of 3D modelling, parametric design and environmental analysis in software familiar to architects and urban planners in order to create environmentally conscious urban designs.

Evaluation of thermal comfort in urban designs of linear street showed that periods with very strong heat stress have decreased on hot summer day up to 9.8 %. In contrast, the greatest thermal stress in winter (strong cold stress) increased up to 6.5 %. UTCI decreased up to 6.1 °C at 10 UTC when comparing past and future urban designs on hot summer day. On cold winter day, greatest UTCI decrease of 3.2 °C was observed at 11 UTC. Noticed maximum UTCI changes occurred on the shadowed body locations.

Improvement of outdoor thermal comfort between future planned and proposed urban design of linear street is a consequence of up to 2.9 °C UTCI decrease on summer day and up to 1.7 °C UTCI increase on winter day. The UTCI decrease in non-linear streets between future planned and proposed urban designs was up to 3.9 °C on summer day and increase was up to 1.1 °C on winter day.

The developed automatic algorithms procedures showed to be suitable for evaluating and improving outdoor thermal comfort in urban environments. A single additional building and its influence on thermal comfort were recognized in the software and in the final results. Using the calculated effects of modified built environment on outdoor thermal comfort, urban areas with the most severe heat and cold stresses can be identified. This information could be useful at the beginning of urban planning process in order to improve outdoor thermal comfort by creating optimal urban design. Furthermore, it is a valuable contribution for urban planning strategies in order to counterattack the adverse effects of urban climate and expected climate change (i.e.

temperature rise).

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Table 1. UTCI assessment scale [20].

UTCI [°C] range	Stress category
Above +46	Extreme heat stress
+38 to +46	Very strong heat stress
+32 to +38	Strong heat stress
+26 to +32	Moderate heat stress
+9 to +26	No thermal stress
+9 to 0	Slight cold stress
0 to -13	Moderate cold stress
-13 to -27	Strong cold stress
-27 to -40	Very strong cold stress
Below -40	Extreme cold stress

Table 2. Surface properties of the 250 m radius environment around measurement station 2-3. The abbreviations refer to surface properties: HRE – height of roughness elements, SVF – sky view factor, BSF – building surface factor, ISF – impervious surface factor, PSF – pervious surface factor, and ALB – albedo.

Name of station	LCZ class	HRE [m]	SVF	BSF	ISF	PSF	ALB	Land use: Corine Land Cover for Novi Sad [21]
2-3	LCZ 2 – compact midrise	16.2	0.5100	0.3381	0.6293	0.0326	0.1677	100% urban discontinuous

Table 3. Methodology for the UTCI calculation in Ladybug.

Phases	Simulations input parameters	Software
1. Geometry	Geometry input: -Buildings -Houses -Footways Referencing geometry inputs	Rhinoceros Grasshopper
2. Calculate Solar Adjusted Mean Radiant Temperature (SAMRT)	Input data for Outdoor Solar Temperature Adjustor: -Air temperature [°C] -Relative humidity [%] -Wind speed [m s^{-1}] -Direct solar radiation [W m^{-2}] -Global solar radiation [W m^{-2}] -Diffuse solar radiation [W m^{-2}] -Body posture -Body rotation [0-360°] -Ground reflectivity [0-1] -Clothing absorptivity [0-1] -Analysis period (00-24h, 1-31 day, 1-12 month) -Context shading (3D geometry) -Body location	Ladybug
3. Calculate UTCI	Input data for Outdoor Comfort Calculator: -Air temperature [°C] -Relative humidity [%] -Wind speed [ms^{-1}] -SAMRT [°C]	Ladybug
4. Numerical results	Detecting all UTCI values: -Hourly UTCI values for each manikin position [°C]	Grasshopper

Table 4. UTCI stress categories [%] for the three urban street designs during a hot summer day (July 7th 2014).

Stress category	Southern footway			Middle of the street			Northern footway		
	Past	Present	Future	Past	Present	Future	Past	Present	Future
Very strong heat stress	17.5	9.6	7.7	21.1	18.2	17.3	21.1	14.7	14.5
Strong heat stress	32.5	30.1	27.6	28.9	28.7	29.6	27.2	31.6	31.8
Moderate heat stress	29.2	39.5	43.9	29.2	30.7	30.7	30.0	29.8	29.8
No thermal stress	20.8	20.8	20.8	20.8	22.4	22.4	21.7	23.9	23.9

Table 5. UTCI stress categories [%] in the three urban street designs on a cold winter day (31st December 2014).

Stress category	Southern footway			Middle of the street			Northern footway		
	Past	Present	Future	Past	Present	Future	Past	Present	Future
Moderate cold stress	67.1	64.0	63.6	67.8	67.1	66.9	68.4	66.9	66.7
Strong cold stress	32.9	36.0	36.4	32.2	32.9	33.1	31.6	33.1	33.3

HIGHLIGHTS

- A parametric approach for urban outdoor thermal comfort is introduced
- Automatic algorithms were developed and applied in Grasshopper
- Building height and density increases reduced the UTCI values
- Shading by buildings decreased (increased) the thermal stress in summer (winter)
- The algorithms are applicable for landscape planning and thermal comfort studies